

Metamaterial or ordinary magneto-electric matter as an energy source for emulation of the Alcubierre Warp Drive for superluminal motion

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Abstract:

In this article, considering the work referenced in [16] that allows for emulation motion up to $\frac{1}{4}$ of the speed of light, appropriate modifications have been considered where by classes of metamaterials or ordinary magneto-electric materials can be used for an emulation Alcubierre drive that permits superluminal motion.

Introduction:

In 1994, Alcubierre [1] proposed a solution to the equations of general relativity that provides the only viable means to accelerate a spaceship to superluminal velocities without using wormholes. However, a problem was soon identified: Pfenning [4] showed that the required energy is comparable to the total energy of the universe and that it is negative. Given the paper [16], we consider a better choice of coordinates to calculate g_x [16] (the magneto-electric susceptibility [20]) of the metamaterial or magneto-electric material in such a way as to satisfy the principles of thermodynamics.

Note: In the following we adopt the notation used by Landau and Lifshitz in the second volume (“The Classical Theory of Fields”) of their well known Course of Theoretical Physics [15].

The starting metric is that of Alcubierre, to which a coordinate transformation has been applied that, in a medium, is:

$$ds^2 = (c/n)^2 dt^2 - (dx - v f(x') dt)^2 - dy^2 - dz^2 \quad (1)$$

performing the coordinate transformation $dx' = dx - v dt$ we have

$$ds^2 = (c/n)^2 dt^2 - (dx' + v g(x') dt)^2 - dy^2 - dz^2 \quad (2)$$

$$g(x') = 1 - f(x')$$

$$ds^2 = \left(\frac{1}{n^2} - \frac{v^2}{c^2} g(x')^2 \right) c^2 dt^2 - dx'^2 - 2v g(x') dx' dt - dy^2 - dz^2 \quad (3)$$

Maxwell's equations in this gravitational field can be written in three dimensions, where D, E, H, and g are vectors [15] and [16]:

$$D = \frac{E}{\sqrt{g_{00}}} + H \times g \quad B = \frac{H}{\sqrt{g_{00}}} + g \times E \quad [15] \quad (4)$$

where $g_{0i} = -g_{0i}/g_{00}$ (vector product \times)

$$\epsilon = \mu = (g_{00})^{(-1/2)} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1/n^2 - (v^2/c^2) g(x')^2}} \quad (5)$$

$$g_x = \frac{(v/c) g(x')}{1/n^2 - (v^2/c^2) g(x')^2} \quad (6)$$

$$g_x^2 \leq (\epsilon - 1)(\mu - 1) \quad (7)$$

$f(r)$ is one inside warp region, is zero outside warped region is $0 < f(r) < 1$ in warped region

Now taking the modified metric:

$$ds^2 = (c/n)^2 dt^2 - \left(dx - v \frac{f(x')}{a(r)} dt\right)^2 - dy^2 - dz^2 \quad (8)$$

and changing the coordinates, which are the most appropriate in this case:

$$dx' = dx - \frac{v}{a(r)} dt \quad \text{found} \quad ds^2 = (c/n)^2 dt^2 - \left(dx' + v \frac{g(x')}{a(r)} dt\right)^2 - dy^2 - dz^2 \quad (9)$$

where $g(x') = 1 - f(x')$ and have $\epsilon = \mu = (g_{00})^{(-1/2)} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1/n^2 - (v^2/c^2) \frac{g(x')^2}{a(r)^2}}} \quad (10)$

$$g_x = \frac{(v/c) \frac{g(x')}{a(r)}}{1/n^2 - (v^2/c^2) \frac{g(x')^2}{a(r)^2}} \quad g_x^2 \leq (\epsilon - 1)(\mu - 1) \quad (11)$$

$a(r) = 1$ inside and outside warped region, $a(r) = A = \text{constant} \gg 1$ in warped region
(discrete case) in the warped region (energy source, metamaterial, or ordinary matter)

analytical case:

$$a(r) = \frac{2^p}{(1 + (\tanh(\sigma(r-R)))^2)^p} \quad p \gg 1 \quad \sigma \gg 1 \quad [17]$$

Under these conditions g_x it can be reduced as desired and thus satisfy the condition (11) of not violating thermodynamics. For the equations, see [15] and [16].

Conclusion:

In this article, it is shown how to emulate a warp drive for superluminal motion using not only metamaterials but also ordinary magneto-electric materials such as Cr_2O_3 , $g_x=1.5 \cdot 10^{-3}$.

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